

Article Arrival Date**10.09.2023****Article Published Date****20.12.2023****PHONETIC RULES IN THE AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE****Assist. Prof. ULVIYYA NASIROVA**

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ABSTRACT

Language is pronounced and heard, written and read with conventional signs-letters. Thus, although language takes forms such as spoken, written, read and heard speech, it is mainly manifested in sounds. As the language changes and develops, the sounds in the language can also change. The change of sounds, which are the material means of the changing language in connection with the development of the society, can lead to the change of a number of phonetic phenomena of the language, and even the creation of new phonetic rules. Therefore, it is important to know the material part of the language, i.e. the sounds, to understand a number of phenomena and laws related to the sounds, in order to study the language both for practical purposes and for theoretical purposes.

Language, whatever its form, always exists in a certain tone. The psychology of speech confirms that the pronunciation and intonation of words and sentences exist in the brain of the writer and reader when a person writes or reads silently. However, during speaking and reading aloud, the sounding of words and sentences, their acoustic images are clearly manifested. Language is realized through meaning, and meaning, in turn, is a means of communication that connects language and the surrounding world. "Foreign linguistics" is generally considered to be the study of speech activity. Teaching a foreign language is a specific means of establishing contact with a foreign socio-cultural environment. Therefore, in order to be able to use the language realistically, the student should also master the cultural facts in addition to the language. In other words, the second goal emerges while learning a foreign language, that is, the student should know the culture of the people who speak that language in addition to the foreign language. This means learning to recognize, understand, and appreciate communicators."

"M. Kopruluzadeh's statement about the Azerbaijani literary language of that period attracts our attention: "Azeri Turkish, or Eastern Oghuz dialect, which was the court and army language of Turkic states such as the Jalalirs, Karakoyuns, Akkoyuns, and Safavids, became a literary language starting from the end of the 13th century." . Later, the author shows that many great poets who originally belonged to the Azeri field, such as Nasimi and Fuzuli, also played a great role in the evolution of Anatolian Turkish literature. (Agamusa Akhundov Phonetics of the Azerbaijani Language p. 5-6)

Keywords: conventional, socio-cultural environment, through meaning

1. INTRODUCTION

In the second period of the history of the development of our literary language, the Azerbaijani language acquired other social qualities. Our literary language of this period was based on the national language since the 19th century. Prominent researcher of the Azerbaijani language Prof. A. Demirchizade writes: "One of the characteristics of this period is that this period lasted for a long time compared to the following periods. However, despite this, compared to later periods, the development rate of the literary language of this period was extremely slow, there were very few changes in the literary language, this literary language was traditionally preserved for a long time, the same type of expressions were repeated for centuries, a number of innovations took place in the national language, almost barely reflected in the literary language." However, despite this, compared to later periods, the development rate of the literary language of this period was extremely slow, there were very few changes in the literary language, this literary language was traditionally preserved for a long time, the same type of expressions were repeated for centuries, a number of innovations took place in the national language, almost barely reflected in the literary language. In another article, prof. A. Demirchizade shows: "One of the specific signs of the literary language of this period is that here synonymous expressions, words, suffixes became common and common; that is, in the literary language of this period, both Arabic, Persian, and Azerbaijani expressions, words, and even suffixes were used side by side to express the same content, the same concept and meaning."

2. METHODOLOGY

As we know, many Arabic and Persian words were used in the Azerbaijani language at that time. The language styles, poetic genres and tools of that period led to the transfer of borrowed words to our literary language and the fact that most of the borrowed words that did not enter the dictionary left the vocabulary of our language." Prof. H. Mirzazade shows that in our modern literary language, interrogative pronouns starting with the sound [h] were used with the sound [q] until the 18th century, mainly in the works of all writers. This is also the case with locative and definite pronouns. Later, the author writes: "We see that the same words were written with [x] instead of [q] in the 15th and a little later centuries."

The basis of the criterion used in determining the norms of literary language are mainly the following: honesty, correctness, precision, ease, simplicity, uniformity, sameness, stability, harmony, fluency and continuity.

"Here it is necessary to mention the fact that the Azerbaijani language was a means of common understanding among the different linguistic peoples living in Central Asia in general, especially in the Caucasus, even in the past centuries, even lovers from a number of Caucasian peoples mainly said their couplets in the Azerbaijani language." (Modern Azerbaijani language A. Demirchizade page 6)

Voice, as a phonetic term, broadly means the sounds produced by the speech organs. Every language has a certain number of sounds. A certain number of sounds in the language are sounds that express a distinctive meaning. Such sounds are called phonemes in linguistics. Phonemes are sounds that make up the material shell of words in the language and distinguish one word from

another as a unit of speech, that is, as a unit of social meaning. Phonemes have a number of properties that distinguish them from other sounds.

Phoneme is an independent link of the language system. It is not separate from the word, but a meaningful unit that can be contained within the word. A phoneme is the smallest unit of language that makes a difference in meaning. A phoneme can consist of one, two or even three sounds (monophthong, diphthong, triphthong). A new phoneme can be formed when one phoneme is processed in the tone of another phoneme.

3.FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

As we mentioned, since the tongue and lips are among the most active members of speech in the production of sounds in all languages, these two members, especially the tongue and lips, are considered the main criterion in the physiological classification of vowel sounds. In phonetics, there are some aspects of both vowels and consonants that require the use of acoustic criteria to clarify them.

Sounds are formed in different denominators. The sounds in the language are grouped on the following basis:

I. The participation of the vocal cords in the generation of sounds is mainly manifested in two cases. There are two types of sounds: vowels and consonants.

In the first case, the vocal cords are extremely strained. The vocal cords vibrate. Such sounds are vowel sounds: a, i, r, l, m, n.

In the second case, the vocal cords are not strained. Such sounds are called consonant sounds: p, f, t, s, sh, k.

II. In the change of sounds in different colors, two situations are decisive in the participation of the mouth parts and are divided into two parts: vowel sounds, consonant sounds

Vowel sounds are pronounced freely and without hindrance. Vowels also form syllables.

Vowel sounds do not encounter any obstacles in the oral cavity: a, ö, e, i, o, ü, u, ə, ɪ

In the pronunciation of consonant sounds, there are various obstacles in the oral cavity.

Consonant sounds are vowels or consonant sounds that are pronounced when one or another part of the mouth is obstructed: n, m, r, b, p, z, s, c, ç, q, x, d, etc.

III. Speech sounds are divided into two groups according to the predominance of tone or tone in the voice: sonorous sounds and noisy sounds.

Sonorous sounds are determined according to resonator tones, that is, in sonorous sounds, the musical tone - voice is dominant: l, r, n, m. Such sounds are formed by encountering an obstacle in the mouth and nasal cavity.

Vowel sounds are classified based on the following principles:

1. According to the horizontal position of the tongue
2. According to the vertical position of the tongue
3. According to the condition of the lips

4. Due to the stability of the denominator
5. According to quantity
6. Due to tension

According to the horizontal position of the tongue, the vowels are divided into three parts: vowels of the tongue, middle, and middle vowels.

In the formation of tongue vowels, the middle part of the tongue rises towards the front palate. Tongue vowels: ə, i, e, ü

The front and middle part of the tongue rises up towards the palate in the formation of dilated vowels. There is only one middle vowel in the Azerbaijani language, which is e.

In the formation of open vowels, the front part of the tongue does not rise, and the lower jaw is lowered. Open vowels: o, ö, a, ə.

Two of the open vowels are thick (a, o), and two are thin (ə, ö).

Among the open and closed vowels in the literary language of Azerbaijan, there is another vowel, which is considered a semi-closed vowel since it has a denominator close to the closed one. In Azerbaijani, e is a semi-closed vowel.

According to the position of the lips, vowels are divided into two parts: lipped and unliped. When pronouncing some vowels, the lips take a small or large round shape. Vowels formed by rounding the lips are called labial vowels (or labial vowels). Sometimes it occurs when the lips are pulled towards the corners of the mouth (when laughing) and thus does not participate in the formation of a number of vowels. Vowels formed without the presence of the lips are called lipless vowels (or palatal vowels). Non-labialized vowels: a, ı, ə, e, i.

Two of the unlipitized vowels (a, ı) are thick, and three are thin (ə, e, i) thin vowels.

According to the stability of the denominator, vowels are of two types: single (monophthong), double (diphthong). Single vowels are formed when the place of origin of the vowel sound does not change until the sound comes out of the mouth. All vowels in the literary language of Azerbaijan are mostly single vowels.

Double vowels (diphthongs) are vowels formed in two vowel denominators and pronounced in one syllable.

There are no fully formed diphthong phonemes corresponding to monophthong vowels in the literary language of Azerbaijan.

Double vowels are vowel phonemes that occur in the quantity of one vowel in two vowel denominators.

Vowels according to quantity: regular vowels, long vowels, short vowels.

There are no fixed long and short vowels in the Azerbaijani literary language. But just as there are vowels in dialects, in literary pronunciation there are lengthenings and shortenings that are to some extent related to orthoepic norms.

It should be noted that the quantitative difference of vowels in literary pronunciation in the modern literary language of Azerbaijan cannot be the reason for the difference in meaning of individual words. Short vowels are vowels that are shorter than the vowels that are normally pronounced. In

some words, the dropping of this or that vowel in the root when receiving a suffix indicates that the dropped vowel is mainly a short vowel; neck-neck, mouth-mouth, etc. Long and short vowels are not considered complete phonemes in the literary language of Azerbaijan. According to stress, vowels are divided into two types: stressed vowels and unstressed vowels. In the pronunciation of tense vowels, the tongue, lips, palate, larynx are very tense, and in this case the denominator and main color of the vowels are also very clear. In the pronunciation of unstressed vowels, the tongue, lips, palate, and larynx are less tense, and in this case the denominator and main color of the vowels are not as clear. In general, regular and short vowels are unstressed. Vowels are of two types due to the flow of air coming out of the oral cavity and nasal cavity: oral vowels and nasal vowels.

One of the main features that distinguish consonants from vowels is the sounds produced by the participation of speech organs in the oral cavity of consonants in different ways. Consonants are divided into two parts according to the amount of noise: sonorous and noisy. Some of the consonants are formed when the flow of sound flows out of the oral or nasal cavity, despite encountering a slight obstruction in the oral cavity. These consonants are tone sounds. Modern Azerbaijani literary language has 4 sonorous consonants: l, r, m, n.

The other part of the consonants is formed when the sound flow is filtered out through the path it opens to overcome the obstacle in the oral cavity. These sounds are called voiced consonants. Voiced consonants: b, p, v, f, g, k, z, s, j, sh, ğ, x, q, |k`|, b, t, y, |x`|, h.

Noisy consonants are divided into two: ringing, deaf.

Sometimes the vocal cords are strained and brought closer to each other during the production of consonant sounds. Such consonants are called voiced consonants.

Voiced consonants: b, v, q, g, d, z, j, g, c.

Sometimes the vocal cords are not strained during the production of sounds, the vocal tract is not narrowed, the ends of the vocal cords are too close to each other. Such sounds are called deaf consonants.

Deaf consonants: (k`), k, p, s, t, f, x, h, ç, sh, (x`).

One of the general phonetic features of the Azerbaijani language is the law of harmony. In the words that start with a dilönü syllable, the following syllables must also consist of dilönu vowels, and in the words that begin with a dilarkha vowel syllable, the following syllables must also consist of dilarkha vowels.

The phonetic structure of the Azerbaijani language is characterized by the preservation of the law of harmony, as in the case of Turkish languages. One of the factors that make our language musical is closely related to the law of harmony. The law of harmony creates conditions for the systematic arrangement of speech sounds. The systematic arrangement of speech sounds forms a morphologically polished language unit. A morphologically polished linguistic unit becomes musical and fluid. The law of harmony also plays an important role in distinguishing the sounds of nature and the sounds of social conversation.

"Prof. A. Demirchizade shows that agglutinative languages are distinguished from other languages by the law of harmony, i.e. the merging of vowels, or rather, the arrangement of vowels in any word, whether thin or thick, and the merging of thin vowels with thin vowels, thick vowels with thick vowels .

In the Azerbaijani language, there is no violation of the phenomena of harmony between the root and the suffix. We should note that this case applies not only between roots and suffixes in the Azerbaijani language, but also to words made up of different amounts of syllables.

Our language does not have a law of harmony due to the vertical position of the tongue. The harmony of vowels is based on two principles: 1) according to the place of origin or the horizontal position of the tongue; 2) due to the participation of the lips. Depending on the place of origin or the horizontal position of the tongue, vowels follow each other according to the thinness-thickness sign: the tone of thin vowels, the tone of thick vowels.

According to the harmony of thin vowels, the other syllables of the words that start with the first vowel syllable also have the first vowel: om-ru-mu-zun, i-yir-min-ci-ler...

4 .CONCLUSION

The phonetic and grammatical structure of the Azerbaijani language, as well as the vocabulary of our language, is changing and developing. This change and development is sometimes generalizing in content and essence. That is, some changes and development in the language are always repeated. Sometimes it has a random nature and has a transient content.

Therefore, the most important, the most necessary, always repeated events and processes in the language are legalized. However, events that do not always repeat, occur by chance, or appear transiently, remain events. With this, some processes in the language become legal, and some become events. Thus, laws and phenomena manifest themselves in language. Laws and phenomena also exist in nature and society. Phenomena manifested in different shades in the phonetic shell of language units are collectively called phonetic phenomena. So, there are such changes in the phonetic shell of our language that they do not take the form of law and remain a phonetic phenomenon. The law is the expression of the most important, always repeated relations between the event and the object.

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